

Original Research Paper

RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF KETOCONAZOLE IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

A simple, precise, economic and accurate isocratic RP-HPLC method has been developed and subsequently validated for the determination of Ketoconazole in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms as per ICH guidelines. The separation achieved on a reversed phase Phenomenex Luna C₁₈, 100A, 5 μ m, 250mmx4.6mm i.d. as a stationary phase and Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer in the ratio of 68:32v/v as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The UV detection was performed at 242 nm. The retention time for Ketoconazole was found to be 4.768min. The detector response was linear in the concentration range of 0-14 μ g/ml. The %RSD for precision and accuracy of the method was found to be less than 2%. The respective linear regression equation being $Y = 72353.x + 5437$ with $R^2 = 0.999$. The limit of detection and the limit of quantification were found to be 0.08 μ g/ml and 0.26 μ g/ml respectively. The method was validated according to the ICH guidelines with respect to specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, LOD and LOQ. The results of the study showed that, the proposed RP-HPLC method was simple, rapid, precise, accurate and stability indicating, which can be used for the routine determination of Ketoconazole in bulk and its pharmaceutical dosage form.

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INTRODUCTION :

Ketoconazole is a synthetic imidazole antifungal drug used primarily to treat fungal infections. Ketoconazole is sold commercially as a tablet for oral administration (although this use has been discontinued in a number of countries), and in a variety of formulations^{1,2,3} for topical administration, such as creams (used to treat tinea; cutaneous candidiasis, including candidal paronychia; and pityriasis versicolor) and shampoos (used primarily to treat dandruff—seborrheic dermatitis of the scalp). Broad spectrum^{4,5} antifungal agent used for long periods at high doses, especially in immuno suppressed patients. It is a racemate consisting of equimolar amounts of (2R,4S)- and (2S,4R)-ketoconazole with the chiral centers on the acetal ring. For the treatment of the following systemic fungal^{6,7,8} infections: candidiasis, chronic mucocutaneous candidiasis, oral thrush, candiduria, blastomycosis,

coccidioidomycosis, histoplasmosis, chromomycosis, and paracoccidioidomycosis.

Ketoconazole interacts with 14- α demethylase, a cytochrome P-450 enzyme necessary for the conversion of lanosterol to ergosterol. This results in inhibition of ergosterol synthesis and increased fungal cellular permeability. Other mechanisms may involve the inhibition^{9,10} of endogenous respiration, interaction with membrane phospholipids, inhibition of yeast transformation to mycelial forms, inhibition of purine uptake, and impairment of triglyceride and/or phospholipid biosynthesis. Ketoconazole can also inhibit the synthesis of thromboxane and sterols such as aldosterone, cortisol, and testosterone. Ketoconazole, like clotrimazole, fluconazole, itraconazole, and miconazole, is an imidazole antifungal agent.

Ketoconazole is chemically^{11,12} 1-[4-(4-{[2-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-2-(1H-imidazol-1-ylmethyl)-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl]methoxy}phenyl)piperazin-1-yl]ethan-1-one. The molecular formula¹³ is $C_{26}H_{28}Cl_2N_4O_4$. The molecular weight¹⁴ is 531.431g/mol.

The main aim and objective is to develop and validate a RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Ketoconazole in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. The developed method successfully can be applied to estimate the amount of Ketoconazole in pharmaceutical dosage^{15,16,17} form. The proposed method was validated as per ICH guidelines^{18,19}. The structure of Ketoconazole was shown in fig-1.

Fig-1: Structure of Ketoconazole

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. LIST OF INSTRUMENTS USED

Table-1: List of Instruments used

S. No.	Instruments/Equipments/Apparatus
1.	Waters HPLC with Empower2 Software with Isocratic with UV-Visible Detector.
2.	ELICO SL-159 UV - Vis spectrophotometer
3.	High Precision Balance (SHIMADZU ATY224)
4.	Ultra Sonicator (Wensar wuc-2L)
5.	Thermal Oven
6.	Phenomenex Luna C ₁₈ , 100A, 5 μ m, 250mmx4.6mm i.d.
7.	pH Analyzer (ELICO)
8.	Vacuum filtration kit (BOROSIL)

Mobile phase Preparation

The mobile phase used in this analysis consists of a mixture of Buffer²⁰ (Potassium hydrogen orthophosphate & pH adjusted to 4.20 with orthophosphoric acid) and Acetonitrile in a ratio of 32: 68. 320 ml of this buffer solution was added and properly mixed with 680 ml of Acetonitrile and a homogenous solution is achieved. This mobile phase was filled and sonicated for 15 minutes before using in the experiment^{21,22}.

Diluent Preparation:

Mobile phase is used as diluent²³.

Sample Solution Preparation:

25mg of Ketoconazole Working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 25 ml

2. LIST OF CHEMICALS, REAGENTS AND STANDARDS USED:

Table-2: List of Chemicals used

S.NO.	Name	Specifications		Manufacturer /Supplier
		Purity	Grade	
1.	Doubled distilled water	99.9%	HPLC	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
2.	Methanol	99.9%	HPLC	Loba Chem; Mumbai.
3.	Dipotassium hydrogen orthophosphate	96%	L.R.	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
4.	Acetonitrile	99.9%	HPLC	Loba Chem; Mumbai.
5.	Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate	99.9%	L.R.	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
6.	Orthophosphoric acid	99.99%	L.R	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai

volumetric flask and about 20 ml of diluent was added to it and sonicated²⁴ to dissolve drug completely and volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent which gave Stock solution of 1000ppm. 1 ml of the above stock solution was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluents to prepare 100ppm solution. Further 1 ml of prepared 100ppm solution was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and was diluted up to the mark with diluents which gave 10ppm Ketoconazole working standard solution. The solution was mixed well and filtered²⁵ through 0.45 μ m filter.

METHODOLOGY

METHOD DEVELOPMENT

Phenomenex Luna C₁₈, 100A, 5 μm, 250mmx4.6mm i.d. used as a stationary phase^{26,27} with a mobile phase of Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer in the ratio of 68: 32 and pH can be adjusted to 4.20 with orthophosphoric acid and a flow rate of 1.0ml/min with detection wavelength²⁸ of 242nm achieved the best separation of Ketoconazole [12-13]. The Ketoconazole standard solution prepared as same like above were injected into the HPLC system and the optimized chromatogram was recorded as shown in fig-2. The retention time^{29,30} of Ketoconazole was found to be 4.768minutes.

ASSAY ESTIMATION OF KETOCONAZOLE IN TABLET

DOSAGE FORM

Twenty tablets were taken and the I.P. method was followed to determine the average weight. Above weighed tablets were finally powdered and triturated well. A quantity of powder equivalent³¹ to 100 mg of drugs were transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, and 70 ml of HPLC grade methanol was added and solution was sonicated for 15 minutes, there after volume was made up to 100 ml with same solvent. Then 10 ml of the above solution was diluted to 100 ml with HPLC grade methanol. The solution was filtered through a membrane filter (0.45 μm) and

METHOD VALIDATION

LINEARITY AND RANGE

To evaluate the linearity³⁴, serial dilution of analyte were prepared from the stock solution was diluted with mobile phase to get a series of concentration ranging from 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14μg/ml. The prepared solutions were filtered through whatmann filter paper (No.41). From these solutions, 20μl injections of each concentration were injected into the HPLC system and chromatographed²⁸ under the optimized conditions. Calibration curve was constructed by plotting the mean peak area (Y-axis)

PRECISION

Repeat ability

The precision³⁶ of each method was ascertained separately from the peak areas & retention times obtained by actual determination of six replicates of a fixed amount of drug. Ketoconazole (API) the percent relative standard deviations were calculated for Ketoconazole is presented in the Table-6.

sonicated to degas. From this stock solution (1.0ml) was transferred to five different 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume was made up to 10 ml with same solvent system^{32,33}.

The solution prepared was injected in five replicates into the HPLC system and the observations were recorded.

A duplicate injection of the standard solution was also injected into the HPLC system and the peak areas were recorded. The data are shown in Table-4.

ASSAY:

Assay % =

$$\frac{\text{AT}}{\text{AS}} \times \frac{\text{DS}}{\text{DT}} \times \frac{\text{P}}{100} \times \text{Avg. Wt} = \text{mg/tab}$$

AS DS WT 100 Where:

AT = Peak Area of Test obtained with test preparation

AS = Peak Area of Standard obtained with standard preparation

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg

WT = Weight of sample taken in mg

DS = Dilution of Standard solution

DT = Dilution of sample solution

P = Percentage purity of working standard

against the concentration (X-axis). The results which are given in Table below were within acceptable limits.

ACCURACY

Recovery study:

To determine the accuracy of the proposed method, recovery studies were carried out by adding different amounts (80%, 100%, and 120%) of pure drug of Ketoconazole were taken and added to the pre-analyzed formulation of concentration 10 μg/ml. From that percentage recovery values³⁵ were calculated. The results were shown in Table-5

Intermediate precision

The intra & inter day variation of the method was carried out & the high values of mean assay & low values of standard deviation & % RSD (% RSD < 2%) within a day & day to day variations for Ketoconazole revealed that the proposed method is precise [20]. The results of intermediate precision were shown in Table-7.

LIMIT OF DETECTION AND LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION

The LOD and LOQ³⁷ were calculated by the use of the equations

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / S$$

and

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Where, σ is the standard deviation of intercept of Calibration plot and S is the average of the slope of the corresponding Calibration plot.

ROBUSTNESS

Influence of small changes in chromatographic conditions such as change in flow rate ($\pm 0.1\text{ml/min}$), Temperature ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), Wavelength of detection ($\pm 2\text{nm}$) & Acetonitrile content in mobile phase ($\pm 2\%$) studied to determine the robustness³⁸ of the method are also in favour of (% RSD < 2%) the developed RP-HPLC method for the analysis of Ketoconazole (API). The results were shown in the Table-8.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig-2: Chromatogram of Ketoconazole Standard Solution

Fig-3: Calibration Curve for Ketoconazole

Table-3: Linearity data of Ketoconazole

S. No.	CONC.	AUC (n=5)
1	0	0
2	6	425874
3	8	565872
4	10	714542
5	12	865632
6	14	1013121

Table-4: Quantitative estimation of Ketoconazole in Tablet dosage form

Brand Name of tablets	Labelled amount of Drug (mg)	Mean (\pm SD) amount (mg) found by the proposed method (n=6)	Mean (\pm SD) Assay (n = 6)
NIZRAL Tablet (Johnson & Johnson)	200	199.463 (\pm 0.06)	99.084 (\pm 0.49)

Table-5: Accuracy data of Ketoconazole

Sample ID	Concentration (μ g/ml)		Peak Area	% Recovery of Pure drug	Statistical Analysis
	Amount Added	Amount Found			
S ₁ : 80 %	8	8.157	595625	101.962	Mean= 101.387% S.D. = 0.516599 % R.S.D.= 0.509532
S ₂ : 80 %	8	8.099	591457	101.237	
S ₃ : 80 %	8	8.077	589875	100.962	
S ₄ : 100 %	10	10.077	734587	100.77	Mean= 100.43% S.D. = 0.833727 % R.S.D.= 0.830157
S ₅ : 100 %	10	9.948	725268	99.48	
S ₆ : 100 %	10	10.104	736524	101.04	
S ₇ : 120 %	12	11.989	872949	99.908	Mean= 100.6997% S.D. = 0.841254 % R.S.D.= 0.835409
S ₈ : 120 %	12	12.190	887456	101.583	
S ₉ : 120 %	12	12.073	878975	100.608	

Table-6: Repeat ability data of Ketoconazole

HPLC Injections	Retention Time (Minutes)	Peak Area (AUC)
Replicates of Ketoconazole		
Replicate - 1	4.765	725542
Replicate - 2	4.768	726334
Replicate - 3	4.773	727283
Replicate - 4	4.768	724365
Replicate - 5	4.768	728387
Replicate - 6	4.767	725342
Average	4.768167	726208.8
Standard Deviation	0.002639	1449.807
% RSD	0.055356	0.19964

Table-7: Intermediate precision of Ketoconazole

Conc. Of Ketoconazole(API) (µg/ml)	Observed Conc. Of Ketoconazole (µg/ml) by the proposed method			
	Intra day		Inter day	
	Mean (n=6)	% RSD	Mean (n=6)	% RSD
8	8.02	1.06	7.89	1.07
10	10.01	0.93	10.06	0.94
12	12.06	0.94	11.96	0.95

Table-8: Robustness data of Ketoconazole

Change in parameter	% RSD
Flow (1.1 ml/min)	0.08
Flow (0.9 ml/min)	0.52
Temperature (27°C)	0.12
Temperature (23°C)	0.17
Wavelength of Detection (244 nm)	0.68
Wavelength of detection (240 nm)	0.73

LOD AND LOQ:

The Minimum concentration level at which the analyte can be reliably detected (LOD) & quantified (LOQ) were found to be 0.080 & 0.260 µg/ml respectively.

CONCLUSION

A sensitive & selective RP-HPLC method has been developed & validated for the analysis of Ketoconazole API.

Finally the developed RP-HPLC method has excellent accuracy, precision and reproducibility.

The results were shows the developed method is yet another suitable method for assay, purity which can help in the analysis of Ketoconazole in different formulations.

So finally this developed method can be used for the routine analysis of Ketoconazole in tablet dosage form in future.

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